

A bipartite hypovirus is the link to the emergence of the mega-hypoviruses carrying helicases from nidovirales

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Hypoviruses are monopartite positive sense ssRNA viruses that have been broadly studied starting from the model *Cryphonectria hypovirus 1*, which induces hypovirulence on its host, the plant pathogen *Cryphonectria parasitica*. In recent years, many new examples of these viruses have been identified and characterized, and recently some hypoviruses with large genomes have been discovered in different fungi, including a new virus infecting *Rhizoctonia solani* that was called *Rhizoctonia solani hypovirus 2* (RsHV2) (Abdoulaye et al. 2021). This virus has a genome size of more than 22 kilobases and it encodes for two putative proteins. Interestingly, the putative protein encoded by ORF 1 has a helicase domain that is related to the one encoded by the nidoviruses. The hypothesis of horizontal gene transfer and rearrangement of the viral genome have been proposed to explain how a virus like *Rhizoctonia solani hypovirus 2* could emerge. Here we show that a putative viral fragment encoding for a protein showing a helicase domain with homology to the one hosted on RsHV2 was characterized in another isolate of *R. solani* collected in Brazil in 2018. This fragment, called *Rhizoctona solani putative virus 2* (RsPV2), was not associated to any viral genome because of the abundance of different viruses detected in the pool of isolates sequenced from a single library (Picarelli et al. 2019). After repeating the RNAseq on IBR16 isolates only, the one with the highest accumulation of (RsPV2) we report here the evidence of an association between RsPV2 and an hypovirus that was called *Rhizoctonia solani hypovirus 9* (RsHV9). The two viral contigs share around 1800 bases on the 5' end of their sequence, showing what seems to be a conserved 5' end-sequence with a length that was previously unreported for RNA viruses. PCR reaction with a forward primer matching the conserved sequence and two specific reverse primers for the putative RNA1 (RsHV9) and RNA2 (RsPV2) confirmed the existence of the two RNA molecules in vivo and that they are not an in-silico assembly artifact. This data could represent a first evidence of a bipartite nature of a hypo-like virus and a first step in the emergence of RsHV2-like viruses, possibly derived from a rearrangement event between the two genomic segment.

Abdoulaye AH, Hai D, Tang Q, Jiang D, Fu Y, Cheng J, Lin Y, Li B, Kotta-Loizou I, Xie J (2021) Two distant helicases in one mycovirus: evidence of horizontal gene transfer between mycoviruses, coronaviruses and other nidoviruses, *Virus Evolution*, 7:1, veab043, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ve/veab043>

Picarelli MASC, Forgia M, Rivas EB, Nerva L, Chiapello M, Turina M and Colariccio A (2019) Extreme Diversity of Mycoviruses Present in Isolates of *Rhizoctonia solani* AG2-2 LP From *Zoysia japonica* From Brazil. *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.* 9:244.doi: 10.3389/fcimb.2019.00244